

From fragmentation to integration: navigating the way towards automated freight transport and logistics

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Abstract

The introduction of novel solutions based on automation in the field of freight transport and logistics appears more and more as a promising way to address the challenges caused by the increasing complexity of global supply chains and the growing demand for quick, efficient delivery of goods. In the majority of applications so far, fragmentation exists in terms of the developed automation, impeding interoperability across different transport modes and operational environments such as ports, hubs and warehouses. Moving towards the realization of end-to-end automated logistics, this paper is part of the on-going work conducted in the context of the EU-funded Horizon Europe AutoMoTIF project that investigates how the existing challenges can be overcome, and seamless automation can be achieved. AutoMoTIF investigates this through the means of four use cases taking place in different simulated operational environments and in which different transport modes are involved. For each use case, the relevant user needs that are co-defined with the stakeholders involved are translated into functional and non-functional technical specifications. Moreover, a new open reference architecture framework for digital twins, one of the most prominent emerging technologies in the field, is proposed, which acts as a critical enabler for the use cases, guiding the implementation of essential functionalities in port automation, logistics optimization and real-time visualization in real-world logistic environments. This research contributes to the vision of a seamlessly integrated logistics ecosystem, where automation is harmonized across different modes of transport to improve safety, efficiency, connectivity and transparency.

Keywords: automation, freight transport and logistics, digital twin, reference architecture

1. Introduction

The European transport sector is a critical economic driver, contributing approximately 5% to the EU's GDP and employing over 10 million people (European Commission, 2024). Freight transport is essential for regional growth and competitiveness and plays a crucial role in supply chain management by facilitating the efficient movement and timely delivery of raw materials as well as complete products (Crainic et al., 2009). The geographic separation between producers and consumers drives the demand for freight transportation (He et al., 2018). As trade has become more and more globalized, traditional road transport has become less practical, and its negative impact on sustainability has been increasingly recognized (e.g. see Nkesah, 2023; Santos et al., 2010), making the exploration of alternative modes of transportation and their combinations essential.

Rising freight demand combined with existing capacity constraints has intensified the negative externalities associated with transportation, including air, noise and visual pollution, congestion, accidents and excessive CO₂ emissions that contribute to climate change (Serrano-Hernández et al., 2017; Demir et al., 2015). These issues have harmful impacts on the economy, public health, and overall quality of life (International Transport Forum, 2021). The importance of efficient and effective transportation is thus becoming evident, as transportation costs constitute a substantial portion of the overall supply chain expenses. As global supply chains become progressively more complex and demands for rapid delivery continuously increase, the need for innovative solutions in freight transport and logistics has never been more critical (Tavasszy, 2020).

The introduction of automation appears as a promising way to address these challenges. For a systematic literature review on the application of automation in logistics see Ferreira and Reis (2023) and for further insights on how automation impacts sustainable development in general see Almusharraf (2025). Terminals and hubs offer ideal controlled environments for the implementation of advanced automation technologies aiming at improving efficiency and capacity. Nevertheless, in most applications so far, the development of automation is fragmented across different transport modes, hindering interoperability and the realization of end-to-end automated logistics. The seamless movement of goods from origin to destination would require integrated operational models and extensive data sharing between different automated systems. Therefore, to fully benefit from the potential of automation, the key would be to follow a more coordinated approach in order to bridge the gaps in how automation is introduced and handled among different transport modes, towards a seamlessly integrated freight and logistics system.

In this direction, the objective of this paper is to identify the benefits as well as the challenges posed by the use of automation in multimodal freight transport and logistics and to introduce a new open reference architecture framework for digital twins, one of the most prominent emerging technologies in the field. Four use cases are employed to extract relevant user needs, understand technological gaps, and to validate the proposed reference architecture at a later stage. The use cases refer to different parts of the freight transport and logistics chain, namely, automated berthing/unberthing of freight vessels, automated port operations, automated shunting as a service-oriented platform, automated multimodal terminal operations.

The paper is mainly based on the on-going research conducted in the context of the AutoMoTIF (Automation towards multimodal transport and integration of freight) project, funded by the Horizon Europe Programme (GA: 101147693). The remainder of the paper is structured as follows; initially, a literature review on how automation is changing freight transport and logistics is presented. Following that the four AutoMoTIF use cases are introduced, outlining their scope as well as potential implementation challenges. The paper continues with the proposed reference architecture and concludes with some insights on how it can be used to move towards seamless automation in multimodal freight transport and logistics.

2. How is automation changing freight transport and logistics?

Automation has brought drastic changes in many different fields, introducing significant opportunities but also bringing new challenges and creating uncertainty, and the field of freight transportation is no exception to this (De Alwis and Nam, 2024). The growing demand for faster, more efficient, and accurate deliveries has driven the adoption of advanced technologies at all stages of the supply chain (Yang et al., 2021). One of the main benefits of the implementation of automation on multimodal freight transportation, includes the optimization of operations, that can lead to time and cost savings (Pollehn et al., 2021), enhanced efficiency and improved resource management. Moreover, it can assist decision-

making and help coordination of operations and scalability of solutions. In terms of safety, automation can reduce the risk of accidents by detecting and preventing mechanical failures and by minimizing employees' exposure to hazardous situations and can provide more extensive control and better access' supervision e.g. in restricted areas of a terminal. Moreover, through automation, human errors can be eliminated and therefore higher accuracy can be achieved; in addition to that, larger volumes of data can be collected faster and with higher precision. Another critical advantage of the use of automation is the effective monitoring of the environmental impact of a terminal or hub, contributing also to raising awareness regarding the importance of limiting emissions (Evmides et al., 2024; Chu et al., 2018).

At the same time, the implementation of automation has a direct impact on the workforce of the freight transportation industry; some restructuring may be needed while other positions might no longer be even necessary. That makes workers often more reluctant to accept automation, as they fear that it might jeopardize their own job (Hellmuth-Sander, 2023) and calls for significant changes in the working culture of organizations, or/and for extensive training of personnel, that can be a costly and time-consuming process (Baimukhanbetova et al., 2023). The high initial investment that might be required for physical and digital infrastructure in order for the automation to work, is often another barrier faced by organizations that are willing to experiment with innovative technologies (Institute of Supply Chain Management, 2024), especially when often a considerable amount of time is required until a noteworthy return on investment is perceived. Another barrier can be the lack of compatibility between existing systems and new automated technologies. High reliance on automated systems can raise concerns about vulnerability to technical failures and the collection and analysis of real-time data can have implications on privacy and data security, due to vulnerability to potential cyber-attacks (Evmides et al., 2024; Chu et al., 2018), which shows the important role of cybersecurity in supply chains (Jeong, 2024).

Ensuring interoperability among different automated processes is an additional key challenge, as inadequate data standardization can impede effective communication and coordination, and what is more, many different stakeholders with diverse backgrounds, aspirations and objectives are involved, making the planning and implementation process of introducing automation particularly challenging. Last not least, interpreting the regulatory and legal framework can pose extra challenges and new frameworks or modifications of the existing ones might be required before proceeding with automation (Evmides et al., 2024; Chu et al., 2018).

Emerging technologies play a crucial role in the introduction and implementation of automated processes, and is through them that automation is being materialized and gaining potential. Several emerging technologies are being used in different applications in the field of freight transport and logistics, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), big data analytics, blockchain (Pesquera, 2024), 5G networks, automated vehicles, automated robot cranes, smart warehousing solutions and advanced traffic management systems. The concept of a Digital Twin (DT) is another emerging technology, the application of which in logistical environments, such as ports and intermodal terminals, has advanced significantly in recent years (Liu et al., 2024). Initially envisioned as basic digital models for visualization and planning, DTs have evolved into sophisticated systems capable of monitoring, simulating, and optimizing operations in real-time (Le and Fan, 2024). It refers to a virtual replica of a physical asset, system, or process that captures data from sensors and IoT devices to reflect the state, history, and behaviour of its physical counterpart (Javaid et al., 2023). While DT technology incorporates real-time data (Attaran et al., 2023), this is not a fundamental requirement in all cases; their key characteristic is the ability to collect, store, and manage data to support simulations, predictive analysis, and prescriptive modelling. This flexible approach enables DTs to operate both with real-time and buffered or historical data, depending on the specific application requirements.

The efficiency gained with the use of the DT technologies is primarily due to the ability to simulate various operational scenarios, allowing stakeholders to identify bottlenecks and optimize resource allocation

without disrupting actual operations. The evolution of Digital Twins can be classified into four stages of technological maturity, each representing an increase in system interoperability, scalability, and autonomy: a) basic digital representation, b) enhanced digital representation, c) connected digital twin, d) autonomous digital twin. The four DT levels and their relationship with the proposed open reference architecture are further discussed in the next section.

3. The AutoMoTIF Use Cases

3.1 Stakeholders involved in the four use cases: identification and mapping

The introduction and adoption of automation in the field of transport and logistics is a multifaceted issue which brings together a large number of stakeholders from diverse backgrounds and with different aspirations, agendas and objectives. According to the definition of Freeman (1984) in his stakeholder theory, that has been widely used in many fields including transportation (e.g. see Huang et al., 2025; Przybylska et al., 2023; Macharis, 2004), the term stakeholder refers to “any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of an organization’s objectives”. Stakeholder identification and mapping emerge as critical components of any transportation-related project as it allows recognizing and engaging with all parties that can potentially influence or are affected by what the project strives to achieve. This process, in addition to facilitating effective communication and collaboration, contributes to being aware of potential conflicts of interest in an initial stage and to developing timely and efficient strategies to resolve them. Involving a wide range of stakeholders from the early stages of the project can be a game-changer regarding the subsequent success of it and the transferability of its outcome (Sanchez and O’Brian, 2024; Prativiera, 2024; Macharis, 2004).

In order to identify all stakeholder categories that could be potentially involved when automation in freight transport and logistics is considered, therefore across all four use cases of the project, a thorough literature review was followed by validation from AutoMoTIF partners, which lead to enrichment or/and removal of some categories of the initial extensive list. For the stakeholder mapping process, the Power-Interest Matrix/Grid was used, a method that has gained increasing acceptance since its introduction by A.L. Mendelow (1981) and has been used widely in transportation studies as well. This method allocates the different stakeholders involved in one of the following four quadrants, based on their level of power (their ability to influence a decision/policy/project etc.) and their interest (concern about the outcome). The results of this process are presented in the following figure (Figure 1):

Figure 1: Power – Interest Matrix presenting the stakeholders involved in automation in freight transport and logistics

3.2 Use Case 1: Automated berthing/unberthing of freight vessels

Definition and scope

Use Case (UC) 1 focuses on investigating the potential advantages of utilizing automation across all phases of the port call process in terms of operational efficiency, safety, and environmental impact. This includes the vessel’s arrival at the port, which encompasses the initial announcement, allocation of berth windows as well as the tugboats assignment. The process continues with the vessel’s manoeuvring and docking, both performed by the assigned tugboats, followed by the stevedoring operations that secure the vessel on the quay to initiate the cargo loading and unloading processes. The undocking and manoeuvring of the vessel as it departs from the port is also included in UC1. The overall aim of the UC is to identify the basic requirements for a seamless automated port call process. To achieve this objective, UC1 will simulate the entire process of berthing and unberthing at a generic port (i.e. container terminal), to replicate the complex interactions among the process key players with the assumption that the operation will be performed by fully autonomous tugboats (i.e., without a master onboard) and that an Automated Mooring System is installed at the quay. The simulation will incorporate various key parameters for the process, such as weather conditions, size of the vessel, number of tugboats, significant wave etc.

Challenges and barriers

The design of UC1 involves various parameters that must be taken into consideration, which significantly increase the complexity of its implementation. Specific challenges that will be encountered during the UC development are the following:

- The realism of the 3D environment: A container terminal layout will be designed in the 3D environment to represent the key aspects of a generic terminal. In particular, static aspects include the quays, the anchorage area, the depth, and the overall terminal layout. Dynamic

aspects, such as traffic density, sea currents, wind speed, and direction, should also be taken into account. The integration of the dynamic aspects increases the complexity of the 3D environment and requires real data for validation purposes. Furthermore, realism must be balanced against speed as greater accuracy may delay the implementation and will also require greater computational power.

- Data collection process: For the execution of UC1, two types of data will be required that will be used in various scenarios. The first type is weather data (e.g., wind speed, wind direction, and current direction and speed), the collection of which may be time-consuming. The second type of data relates to the movement of the tugboats, which will be used to calibrate and validate the autonomous navigation algorithms of the tugboats. However, the collection process is quite complex and time-consuming, as tugboat-owning companies do not easily share this type of data.
- Integration of tugboat control algorithms into the 3D environment: The development of the manoeuvring algorithms responsible for controlling the tugboats is a separate process from the design and development of the 3D environment, which includes the vessels, the terminal, and sea and weather conditions. These algorithms will be based on machine learning and will require a significant amount of time for training and validation, depending on the available computational power, which may cause delays in the implementation.

3.3 Use Case 2: Automated port operations

Definition and scope

Use Case 2 focuses on exploring the benefits of automating port terminal processes through simulation, using real-world data from the Port of Bilbao, Spain. It will integrate historical data with a simulation model to replicate current baseline operations performance with aspirations of being compared to its automated counterpart. Hence, the simulation will assess various operational objectives, showcasing how automation might affect different aspects of the terminal such as vessel handling, cargo operations, vehicle flow, and logistics efficiency. By simulating these scenarios, UC2 aims to identify an optimal configuration of the terminal operations that reduces inefficiencies, lowers environmental impact, and enhances synchronization within the logistics chain. The aim of the UC is to provide the port with a simulation environment that allows it to assess any economic and/or execution time benefits of applying certain automation to its logistics processes, without incurring the costs and inconveniences of carrying out a real feasibility test on-site. Among the variety of activities that take place in port terminal operations, this use case will focus on the operations encompassing from the arrival of the vessel to the storage of the cargo, simulating the following main processes: loading and unloading, transfer of cargo to the warehouse, cargo handling and shunting operations and warehouse operations.

Challenges and barriers

The potential challenges and barriers which may be faced during the development of the UC2 are described below:

- Impact of the workforce: the shift toward automated port operations may spark conflicting reactions among workforce due to cultural misperception of technological innovation and changes. Overcoming this barrier may necessitate of support and qualified skills development to foster progressive and positive adoption of the implementations which will ease workforce to perceive the potential benefits.
- High Initial Investment: the automation of the exhibited port operations not only require advanced and costly equipment, but also a robust digital infrastructure enabling seamless

integration and implementation. Moreover, due to port operational volumes, the adaptation phase may cause temporary losses while in the long term will be compensated.

- Infrastructure and interoperability issues: the port of Bilbao as a multipurpose terminal deals with a wide variety of cargo which translates into heterogeneous operational schemes. Consequently, the inconsistent standardization presents challenges in data management and security to ensure the integration with existing systems.
- Regulatory and community barriers: implementing automation requires aligning diverse stakeholder interests, establishing clear procedures, and providing training for oversight. Changes may impact supply chain partners, requiring careful coordination. Additionally, liability determination and navigating regulatory frameworks pose challenges, potentially needing new legal standards.

3.4 Use Case 3: Automated shunting as a service oriented-platform

Definition and scope

Use Case 3 explores the implementation of autonomous technologies on an inland terminal dedicated to intermodal freight, focusing on optimizing current and future operational flows at the Magli Intermodal Service (MIS) terminal in Brescia, Italy. The terminal has a complex and constraining layout; it is currently undergoing expansion and, within 10 years, will feature a significantly larger infrastructure. The UC's scope includes simulating the terminal's anticipated layout and operations to assess the potential impact of automation in handling the expected traffic. This approach replicates the terminal's current and future configurations and provides a comprehensive representation of anticipated operations. By incorporating potential operating procedures that have not been implemented, it enables an exploration of how automation may enhance the terminal's efficiency, adaptability, and overall capability to meet evolving demands. Furthermore, simulating automation allows us to introduce the optimization of features that are inherently connected with autonomous solutions.

UC3 aims to evaluate and advance the implementation of automation in intermodal freight transport. Studying the introduction of automation using simulations for both the current and future terminal setups allows for a detailed comparison of its effectiveness in different scenarios, highlighting potential benefits and challenges. By simulating these operations, critical factors that influence efficiency can be identified and addressed early, ensuring the terminal is well-prepared for future demands. Notably, many roles and equipment required in the future are not yet in place, presenting an opportunity to avoid some common setbacks associated with automation. This can be achieved by investing directly in the appropriate equipment, personnel training, and developing best practices, while designing process flows from the ground up.

Challenges and barriers

The development of UC3 faces several challenges and obstacles that need to be carefully managed to ensure the successful implementation of automation in terminal operations.

- One of the main difficulties is the high economic cost of deploying automated systems, such as DAC, locomotives, gates, IGVs, and shunting equipment. The initial investment required for acquiring new technologies, upgrading infrastructure, and ensuring integration with existing operations is considerable. While automation can lead to long-term improvements in efficiency and cost savings, the financial feasibility of such investments remains a key concern. This challenge is especially relevant in those terminals whose volume of operations is reduced.
- Another challenge is the integration of automated systems with third-party trains and existing infrastructure. Since external rail operators use the terminal, automated DAC and shunting

processes must be able to interact smoothly with manually operated trains. Ensuring this level of interoperability requires careful planning, coordination among stakeholders, and the establishment of clear communication protocols to prevent operational conflicts and inefficiencies.

- Legal and regulatory barriers also pose significant difficulties, particularly for automated locomotives and other autonomous systems. Current rail regulations may not fully accommodate automation, leading to potential legal uncertainties and delays in obtaining necessary approvals. Liability issues, safety oversight, and regulatory compliance must be addressed to ensure that automation can be safely and legally integrated into the terminal's daily operations.
- The introduction of an automated gate system, such as IGV, is seen as one of the most promising advancements, as it could help reduce human error and improve overall efficiency. However, its success depends on its ability to correctly identify trains, process data accurately, and operate smoothly alongside existing manual processes. Any technical shortcomings in these areas could lead to delays or operational inefficiencies that would reduce the expected benefits of automation.
- Shunting operations present additional complexities, especially in relation to the type of equipment required. The current shunting locomotives are diesel-powered since the terminal tracks are not electrified, meaning any automated solution must be compatible with this existing limitation or assuming the terminal will be electrified. Additionally, speed restrictions need to be considered, as safety regulations limit shunting operations to 5 km/h in areas with personnel and 10 km/h in low-risk zones. Any automated system must be capable of operating within these constraints while maintaining efficiency.

3.5 Use Case 4: Automated multimodal terminal operations

Definition and scope

Use Case 4 employs a simulation model to evaluate the impact of a new automated intermodal terminal design, featuring the Autonomous Wagon Train (AWT) concept to improve cargo movement between different transport modes, on the Northern Terminal Bremerhaven GmbH in Germany. Terminals require faster, more seamless cargo transfers between rail, road, and sea transport to keep up with growing logistics demands. By allowing autonomous wagons to directly interact with Automated Straddle Carriers (ASCs), the automation not only enhances operational efficiency but also paves the way for smarter, more sustainable intermodal terminal operations. This system represents a leap forward in logistics technology, promising substantial improvements in speed, cost, and safety for container terminals. The simulation will take current traffic conditions as input to assess the effectiveness of this innovative approach. UC4 aims to provide an overview of the impact of applying innovative automation technologies on the operational efficiency of an intermodal terminal. To achieve this, simulation models will be used with two terminal designs, considering combinations of alternative traffic flows. Moreover, the UC will provide input on the requirements for implementing yard automation technologies to optimize the efficiency of the terminal's multimodal operations, enhance sustainability, and reduce environmental footprint.

Challenges and barriers

The potential challenges and barriers which may be faced during the development of the UC4 are described below:

- **Technological complexity:** Developing and integrating sophisticated autonomous navigation systems within the existing terminal infrastructure will be challenging and require extensive testing.
Regulatory Hurdles: Adapting current regulations to accommodate autonomous vehicles operating in dense, complex environments like container terminals may be time-consuming.
- **High Initial Investment:** While long-term cost savings are significant, the initial outlay for developing and implementing these autonomous systems can be substantial.
- **Change Management:** Transitioning to this new system will necessitate substantial adjustments to operational procedures and comprehensive personnel training. Alternative workforce utilization models should be developed to retain the terminal's workforce while simultaneously creating new, high-skilled positions.

4. The AutoMoTIF Open Reference Architecture for Digital Twins

The Open Reference Architecture is designed to overcome the limitations of traditional closed systems, in which components are tightly coupled and proprietary, meaning that integrations with external systems, modules, or technologies are either not possible or require significant customization. These architectures are typically confined to a specific vendor or platform, limiting flexibility, adaptability, and scalability. In contrast, an open architecture provides a framework that is modular, interoperable, and expandable. It is “open” in the sense that it enables the seamless integration of external components, tools, and technologies from various providers, making it highly adaptable to the evolving needs of organizations. This openness does not imply that the system is “free” or unregulated; instead, it refers to the system’s ability to interoperate with diverse external modules while maintaining a standardized core. (Klar, 2023)

In that way, the core principles of an Open Architecture for Digital Twins are the following:

- Modularity
- Interoperability
- Scalability
- Vendor Independence
- Future-Proofing

By following these principles, three layers have been designed as follows:

1. Outer Layer: Integration and Interoperability with External Systems
2. Middle Layer: Core integration and communication functionalities
3. Inner layer: Core functionalities of the Digital Twin

The architecture’s design ensures that all three layers work cohesively to deliver a comprehensive, interoperable, and scalable Digital Twin. Its modular nature allows for the independent upgrading and replacement of components, while its interoperability ensures seamless integration with diverse systems. Additionally, its scalability supports growth and the integration of advanced functionalities as technology evolves. By adopting this reference architecture, organizations can build Digital Twins that are not only capable of real-time monitoring and optimization but also adaptable to future advancements and operational needs. This framework is essential for advancing through the Digital Twin maturity levels, from basic digital representations to autonomous systems.

The Open Reference Architecture for Digital Twins provides a modular and scalable framework that enables the integration and progression of Digital Twin functionalities across their maturity levels, as illustrated in the Digital Twin Levels (Klar, 2024) diagram below. This diagram highlights how capabilities such as data acquisition, integration, simulation, optimization, and user interaction evolve from static representations (Level 1) to fully autonomous systems (Level 4), while emphasizing the growing focus on interoperability with external systems.

This architecture serves as a critical enabler for the four use cases described in section 3, where it guides the implementation of essential functionalities in port automation, logistics optimization, and real-time visualization. By supporting seamless integration with IoT devices, AI models, simulation engines, and legacy systems, the architecture provides the tools needed to achieve greater levels of automation and decision-making efficiency.

Through its scalability, the Open Reference Architecture ensures that these use cases can progressively activate and expand functionalities as they move towards higher levels of Digital Twin maturity. It lays the foundation for transforming port operations, streamlining logistics networks, and enhancing supply chain visibility, aligning each use case with the maturity progression and interoperability focus outlined in the diagram below (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Digital Twin Levels with Open Reference Architecture (Klar 2024, Authors elaboration)

The diagram represents the progressive maturity of Digital Twins, highlighting how the Open Reference Architecture facilitates the activation of critical capabilities at each level. The Open Reference Architecture ensures that Digital Twins at every level can evolve incrementally while maintaining

compatibility with existing systems. As seen in the diagram, the architecture's modular and scalable design enables the progressive activation of capabilities, ensuring that organizations can seamlessly transition to higher levels of maturity without disruption.

This approach empowers organizations to:

- Build flexible systems at early stages that can grow in complexity.
- Achieve full interoperability and autonomy at the highest levels.
- Leverage cutting-edge technologies to optimize operational efficiency, enhance decision-making, and maximize scalability.

5. Conclusions

This paper has examined the fragmented state of automation across multimodal freight transport and logistics and proposed a structured approach to overcome this challenge through the development of an open reference architecture framework. Conducted in the context of the Horizon Europe AutoMoTIF project, this research comprises four distinct use cases that explore the application of automation in diverse logistics environments - from ports and inland terminals to multimodal hubs. These cases provide valuable insights into both the technological potential and the operational, regulatory, and cultural barriers that must be addressed for automation to be adopted on a wider scale.

The proposed open reference architecture offers a robust and adaptable foundation for integrating automation solutions across different transport systems and modes. By enabling modularity, interoperability, and scalability, the framework supports the progressive implementation of advanced functionalities and aligns with the increasing complexity and demands of the logistics sector. Moreover, by connecting real-time data, simulation tools, and stakeholder needs, it facilitates informed decision-making, enhances coordination, and improves system transparency. The research presented herein contributes to the vision of a seamlessly automated, interconnected logistics ecosystem, by proposing a basis for the realization of end-to-end integration across the freight transport chain, supporting the transition toward smarter, more sustainable, and more resilient supply networks.

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